

Non-coding RNAs in Cancer Diagnosis and Therapy

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Cancer is one of the major causes of death all around the world. Cancer invasion comprises a heterogeneous series of basal stages, each of which differs in its type with respect to its dependence on different carcinogenic pathways. To date, various types of RNAs have been explored in cancer research. Recent reports suggest the role of non-coding (ncRNAs) as key regulators of gene expression. They affect a number of oncogenic pathways through a variety of epigenetic mechanisms. These regulatory RNAs make up a large part of the human transcriptional system and are reported to play an important role in tumor physiology and pathogenesis. Increasing evidence on the functional role of ncRNAs in cancer progression indicates their potential in cancer therapy. Although small ncRNAs remain the most studied ones, long ncRNAs are also been explored for possible application in the development of cancer therapeutics. Here, we review the potential roles of different types of ncRNAs in cancer research, focusing on their clinical relevance in cancer therapy, prognosis, and diagnosis.

Keywords: long non-coding RNAs, miRNAs, Cancer diagnosis, Cancer gene regulation, Oncogenic pathways.